

Comparative Analysis of Production efficiencies of Palm oil Production of Coastal belt of Sindh, Pakistan compare with Malaysia and Thailand

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Abstract:

This research investigates the Comparative Analysis of Production efficiencies of Palm oil Production of Coastal belt of Sindh, Pakistan compare with Malaysia and Thailand. Data were collected from primary as well as secondary sources. A structural questionnaire were developed for the reliability and validity of data. It was revealed that According to results in Malaysia is the leading in terms of production efficiencies 16-18 bunches of the one plant and in Thailand 10-15-bunches per plant and total production from one plant 80-90 Kg per plant in Malaysia and 50-60 kg in Thailand. In kathore Farm Thatha Sindh Pakistan production per plant from 55-60kg and in some some plants 14-16 bunches. It was revealed that in short span of time Coastal belt of Thatha is improving plam oil production. Government has to install oil extract mills in coastal belts of Thatha and Badin.

Key Words: Palm Oil, Production Efficiency, Coastal, Sindh, Malaysia, Thailand.

Introduction: Coastal Development Authority Created through an Act passed by the Sindh Provincial Assembly in the year 1994 and later Amended in 2006.

Objectives are: Overall development, improvement and beautification of coastal areas of Thatta & Badin District.

Oil palm-derived oil is now the world's major source of vegetable oil and fat, with over 37 million metric tons produced in 2005, around 27% of the total global production. The oil is ubiquitous in the food industry as well as the oleochemical industry, where it is used for making soaps and detergents. Oil palm is a tropical crop and is cultivated in lowland areas from South America to Africa and Asia. Malaysia and Indonesia are the leading producers of palm oil, exporting 15.0 and 14.1 million metric tons respectively in 2005 [2]. Oil palm production is therefore centered on highly biodiverse regions with high levels of endemism [3]–[5]. Higher levels of palm oil production are also generally associated with a higher number of endangered species. Malaysia has by far the highest levels of palm oil production per unit area and the highest relative number of endangered species (Fig. 1). Recent decades have seen a diversification in the uses of palm oil, for example in feed for livestock and fisheries. Alternative uses for the oil and for byproducts of the plantation system are also being investigated, with interest focusing on their potential as a source of biofuel.

❖ Sindh Coastal Development Authority receives its Non-Development Budget as “One Line” to the tune of Rs.23.463 Million Annually.

Development Budget is provided by Sindh Government through Annual Development Programme (ADP), as well as Foreign Donors. It is worth mentioning here that the Sindh Coastal Development Authority has executed a mega project titled “Sindh Coastal Community Development Project (SCCDP)” funded by Asian Development Bank (ADB) during the year 2008-2013.

Palm oil Production in Malaysia

In order to provide a better understanding of various issues pertaining to forest conversion and the edible oils sector, a study was undertaken on the supply chain of the palm oil industry in Malaysia. The study is divided into two sections, Part A gives an overview of the palm industry and the players in the supply chain while Part B provides detailed information on the various players. The major players in the industry can be grouped into clusters covering upstream producers, downstream producers, exporters and importers, customers, Government agencies and other players such as NGOs. Among these, upstream producers and customers, particularly institutional buyers and investors would be of more direct relevance to the issue of conversion of HCVFs. Of the 3.38 million hectares of oil palm planted in Malaysia in 2000, 60% were under private ownership, particularly by plantation companies, 30.5% were under Government land schemes while the remaining 9.5% are individual smallholders. The largest upstream player is the Federal Land Development Authority (Felda) which was established in 1956 with the socio-economic mandate of developing agricultural land for the rural poor and landless. Felda accounts for 17.7% of the total planted area and 20.6% of the palm oil produced in Malaysia in 2001. Plantation companies vary considerably in size, from a few hundred hectares to more than 100,000 hectares. The five largest companies in terms of planted area are Kumpulan Guthrie Berhad, Golden Hope Plantations Berhad, IOI Corporation Berhad and Sime Darby Berhad. Many present day plantation

companies have their beginnings in the colonial era at the turn of the 20th century when English and other European entrepreneurs transformed forest land into tea and coffee and rubber estates. Amongst the ‘old’ companies are Kumpulan Guthrie Berhad, Golden Hope Plantations Berhad, Sime Darby Berhad, Kuala Lumpur Kepong Berhad and United Plantations Berhad. Since the 1970s, several ‘home grown’ companies have entered the industry, the most notable example being IOI Corporation Berhad which started from zero base in 1983 to become one of the largest plantation companies today.

Data Collection Methodology

Data were collected from primary as well as Secondary sources. A structural questionnaire were developed for the reliability and validity of data.

Results: results shows that per plant production efficiencies of palm oil production in Kathore farm, Malaysia Tekum farm and Thailand farm production were personally observed. Coastal development Authority went Malaysia and Thailand under the innovative leader Iqbal Nafees Khan Director General and Zamir Ujjan deputy Director and his team visited Malaysia and Thailand for two weeks.

According to results in Malaysia is the leading in terms of production efficiencies 16-18 bunches of the one plant and in Thailand 10-15-bunches per plant and total production from one plant 80-90 Kg per plant in Malaysia and 50-60 kg in Thailand.

In Kathore Farm Thatha Sindh Pakistan production per plant from 55-60kg and in some some plants 14-16 bunches. It was revealed that in short span of time Coastal belt of Thatha is improving palm oil production.

Conclusions: This research focus on Production efficiency of Palm oil production in Kathore farm compare with Malaysia and Thailand.

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